

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

D3.2 CALL OF STARTUPS/ SMEs DOCUMENTATION

Revision: v.1.0

Work Package	WP 3
Due date	30/11/2020
Submission date	14/12/2020
Deliverable lead	F6S
Version	1.0
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Abstract	This deliverable contains the Open Call #1 definition, guidelines for applicants and all templates to support Application and programme execution
Keywords	COVID-X, COVID-19, FSTP

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
V1.00	14/12/2020	Approved version of the documentation package	All consortium partners
V1.01	18/12/2020	Updated typos in Annex 2 and Annex 4	F6S AUS
V1.02	04/01/2021	Updated typos in Annex 2	F6S AUS

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the H2020 Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:		R
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	X
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

DOCUMENT SCOPE AND STRUCTURE

The purpose of this document is to compile all the documents that formalize the third-party financing rules for the first COVID-X open call.

- **Annex 1:** Open Call text, which provides a full set of information regarding the Open Call.
- **Annex 2:** Guidelines for Applicants, which provides the scope and objectives of the open call,
- **Annex 3:** Proposal Template, an online application form, available at F6S platform (<https://www.f6s.com/covid-x>)
- **Annex 3.1:** Proposal Supplement, template of a word document providing technical information on proposal including schedule, timing, Ethical & Security details
- **Annex 4:** Honour Declaration, which declares that all conditions of the Open Call are accepted by an SME legal representative.
- **Annex 5:** SME Declaration, which evaluates the status of the SMEs participating at an open call
- **Annex 6:** Bank account information, which collects information on the applicant(s)' bank account where the COVID-X payments will be sent to. Will need to be provided if the proposal is accepted.
- **Annex 7:** Sub-grant Agreement Template, which provides a template of the sub-grant agreement that the successful applicants will be requested to sign.
- **Annex 8:** TEMPLATE for H2020 Financial Support to Third Parties, which contains the formal announcement to be published in the EU portal.

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GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 1: OPEN CALL TEXT

Revision: v.1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016065

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1 Introduction

COVID-X will bridge the collaboration divide between eHealth solution providers -with emphasis on lean startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)-, and the healthcare professional system to fight COVID-19. The purpose is to boost an end-to-end agile validation programme of cutting-edge technology in three real-world clinical scenarios, located in hotspots of the pandemic: Italy, Spain and Sweden.

The project will fast-track value streams between the two poles under consideration: 1) attract, invest and empower a community of European eHealth SMEs –the beneficiaries of an acceleration program, selected by open calls- that will provide market-ready fast, cost-effective and easily deployable sampling, screening, diagnostic and prognostic systems and/or data-driven services and tools, already certified with -or close to receive- the CE marking (type 1 of the call); 2) actively involve some of the most relevant hospitals of Europe that have the resources, critical mass and ambition to scale-up their capabilities in the COVID-19 response; thanks to the support of an innovative data sandbox, released as an in-house asset of COVID-X, to facilitate access easily, uniformly and securely to various health data sources, and providing data services including Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based decision support systems, data security, visual analytics and intuitive dashboards capabilities. The project will invest dedicated efforts to enforce data privacy and security, ethical compliance and user acceptance.

Besides a solid consortium to access high-level startups/SMEs, deliver highly valuable technological & business services, provide an innovative data Sandbox with AI capabilities for COVID related services and access 3 piloting sites, COVID-X targets to attract +155 applications and select 31 to undertake through the COVID-X Programme, investing a total of 4M€ in high impact solution providers.

COVID-X organizes two acceleration programmes to attract, select and fund the best of the best SMEs to test data-driven and AI products, processes, and business models with strong potential in fighting the Covid-19 pandemic.

1.1 COVID-X approach

COVID-X aims to provide competitive and market oriented European SMEs access to **knowledge, technology, capital and markets** with the aim to place new products/ services in the market with the goals of fighting the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 1 COVID-X stages

Figure 2: COVID-X Overall process

The goal of the COVID-X project is to select and fund 13 single solutions and 18 team solutions. The programme is divided in 3 sprints of 3 months each.

The indicative number of projects to be funded in Open Call #1 is 7 Single Solutions and 8 Team Solutions. The number of projects funded may be different depending on the number and quality of the applications received.

It should be underlined that the final number of proposals entering the programme may be different e.g. in case of any Force Majeure such as any unforeseeable exceptional situation.

1.2 COVID-X Pilot sites

The single solutions will be validated at one of the three project pilot sites that belong to the COVID-X Consortium. These sites are located in Italy, Spain and Sweden, and each site is focused on the specific clinical challenges.

Istituto Clinico Humanitas

Location. Milan, Italy

Profile. Istituto Clinico Humanitas (ICH) provides healthcare services for about 1 million patients/year. During COVID-19 pandemic, ICH treated 3,000 patients (about 150 ICU, 1,000 hospitalized and 2,000+ managed by ER).

Objective. Fast, accurate and combined analysis of clinical data available in ER, diagnostic imaging (CT for ICH) and historical profile of patients. Detecting, classifying and treating infected patients as early as possible. Efficient patient-centered diagnostic and AI-based solutions for cross analysis between clinical and radiological data to assess personalized clinical paths and treatments.

Resources. Combination of CTs and aggregated datasets (90+ features per patient), viral load, clinical records and real historical data from the first COVID-19 wave from ICU, hospitalized patients and ER department. Anonymized clinical records will be available in Italian.

Hospital Clinico San Carlos

Location. Madrid, Spain

Profile. Hospital Clinico San Carlos is a tertiary care center covering a population of 300K+ citizens. From the beginning of the pandemic, this centre has attended 3,000+ hospitalized patients diagnosed with COVID-19.

Objective. The main interest of the health professionals caring for hospitalized patients with COVID-19 is to be able to swiftly and precisely diagnose this condition and assess its prognosis. In particular, the hospital is interested to identify “exceptions to the rule”; i.e. subjects belonging to risk groups but who will fully recover with no or minor complications, and vice versa.

Resources. Real-world data generated at the emergency department, hospitalization and Intensive Care Unit, including: codified diagnoses, comorbidities, procedures at discharge (ICD10), codified treatment during stay, admin data on admission and discharge (and motive), admission at ICU, radiology images, and microbiology tests (e.g. Polymerase Chain Reaction). Clinical notes can be accessible in plain text (Spanish).

Karolinska Institute

Location. Stockholm, Sweden

Profile. Karolinska Institutet (KI) is one of the world’s leading medical universities, advancing knowledge about life and striving towards better health for all. KI is Sweden’s single largest centre of medical academic research and offers the country’s widest range of medical courses and programmes. Since 1901 the Nobel Assembly at KI has selected the Nobel laureates in Physiology or Medicine.

Objective. KI aims to enhance the data collection from patients with potential COVID-19 diagnosis, meaning enhancing the pre-diagnostic processes and clinical pathways with AI based developed components

Resources. KI will use its CLEOS software program for history-taking to acquire a COVID-19 related medical history from any patient desiring an acute medical consultation because the patient is experiencing an intercurrent, non-specific illness, e.g., fever, cough, abdominal pain, for fears they have COVID-19 infection. CLEOS will be used by patients contacting the program's COVID-19 portal from home and by patients presenting to emergency departments (ED) in Stockholm.

1.3 COVID-X technological infrastructure

COVID-X envisions the provision of the COVID-X Services and Data Sandbox, COVID-X Sandbox, as the enabling core data-driven technological platform for aggregating, curating, structuring, cataloguing and providing seamless access to anonymized health data from historical data sets of Clinical partners, and, when needed, to data from open data sources, as well as to streaming data from connected medical devices. These are augmented by security, information visualization and data analytics services. The purpose of the COVID-X Sandbox is to provide the core services both to Clinical partners/data providers to ingest data into the Sandbox, and to Third Parties/Solution Providers to integrate their solution with the Sandbox and consume data.

The COVID-X Sandbox is based on a highly modular architecture, built as a mesh of containerised microservices, each of which is running in a Kubernetes cluster. The key advantages of this architectural approach are that it offers simplicity in building and maintaining applications, flexibility and scalability, while the containerized approach makes the applications independent of the underlying system. Figure 1 presents an overview of the building blocks that comprise the architecture of the 1st release (MVP) of the COVID-X Sandbox. Each component within the Sandbox architecture implements and delivers one or more of the aggregated Sandbox services, which for the 1st release are: i) data integration, ii) data harmonization, filtering and cataloguing, iii) data storage, querying and retrieval, iv) security in data access, v) data visualization, vi) API gateway for interaction with third party solutions. Instances of the COVID-X Sandbox will be installed at the provided infrastructure of Clinical partners.

Figure 1 The COVID-X Sandbox Architecture, 1st Release (MVP) – single instance at a local Clinical partner infrastructure

1.4 COVID-X Acceleration services

The third-party technology providers selected in the COVID-X open calls will enter the CovidProgramme. This programme has been specifically designed to provide capacity-building support services to validate and accelerate the market uptake of the selected solutions in the fight against COVID-19.

Specifically, during the programme, the COVID-X consortium partners will provide a wide range of free support services based on the identified and concrete needs of the selected applicants. These tailor-made services will be specified during the onboarding phase and company's analysis and can go from business, technical and technology trainings to mentoring and coaching sessions, tech courses, demo-days, info sessions and others.

CovidProgramme will follow the already mentioned three sprints approach: 1) Onboarding the technology provider where an initial analysis of the business maturity and needs, matchmaking with appropriate testbed and business mentor takes place; 2) Capacity building where technology mentoring and business development roadmap creation takes place; 3) Acceleration and implementation of roadmap with the involvement of technology and business mentors.

2 Scope of projects to be funded

The COVID-X project is funded in the scope of the call H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B¹, specifically type 1 projects of the two COVID-19 areas mentioned below.

To summarize, projects to be funded by type the COVID-X project must be close-to-market (TRL 7+) in the two COVID-19 areas mentioned below and that have already received, or are about to receive, the CE marking to proceed to large scale testing, piloting and deployment operations in critical healthcare areas (or wherever else is relevant).

The areas that COVID-X project is covering are:

- fast, cost-effective and easily deployable sampling, screening, diagnostic and prognostic systems, including new methods for screening of lungs, using for example AI or advanced photonics solutions, to detect the presence of the pathogen related parameters especially in an early stage of infection;
- innovative data-driven services and tools combining data assets from various relevant privately held and/or publicly available sources. These could include AI-based solutions exploiting such data and possibly additional sensor-based signals, for diagnostics, prevention, treatment, or rehabilitation. Where appropriate, privacy, data protection and anonymity in the use of mobile warning and prevention applications, as referred to in the Commission Recommendation C(2020) 2296 of 8 April 2020 on a common Union toolbox for the use of technology and data to combat and exit from the COVID-19 crisis, should be ensured.

¹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B

2.1 Challenge 1 - Early Detection

Early stage detection is crucial to avoid further spread of the disease, reducing the onset of complications and the need for hospitalization. More sophisticated decision-making mechanisms are needed to identify target/priority groups (e.g. subjects more likely to suffer from COVID-19 or those at risk of a worse clinical outcome), reinforcing massive testing.

2.2 Challenge 2 - Innovative Diagnostics

Detection of SARS-CoV2 RNA in different secretions is the current gold standard for COVID-19 diagnosis, but with margins of error and delay. Leveraging the power of machine learning or other deep learning approaches to data analysis, new methods for diagnosis can boost the capability, time-response and improve decision-making processes, complementing the effectiveness of PCR testing.

2.3 Challenge 3 - Personalized Care

A timely and accurate prediction of the course of the disease is a key element to improve the effectiveness of treatment and optimize the resources of the healthcare system. The precision of clinical path increases with retrospective data from previous COVID-19 patients, reinforced with the clinical records of the patient.

2.4 Challenge 4 - Remote Care

Subjects diagnosed with a positive prognosis (e.g. mild symptoms and asymptomatics) can be monitored remotely, contributing to reduce saturation at hospitals and reducing risks for spreading the virus. Continuous monitoring of these cases requires timely and swiftly reaction, adopting user design principles and making such experience trustworthy and human-centric.

2.5 Challenge 5 - Healthcare Continuity

Care levels and specialties are data silos. Health professionals should rely on up-to-date and precise information about the processes undergone by the subjects during their disease, especially cases suffering new episodes (i.e. reinfections) and/or the chance of suffering from chronic complications.

2.6 Challenge 6 – Recovery

A significant proportion of subjects that have overcome COVID-19 remain symptomatic, with manifestations interfering with their daily life activities. We need to empower these subjects and to deliver interventions (e.g. rehabilitation) in ways that do not strain the healthcare and/or social system further.

2.7 Open challenge

Team solutions can address challenges #1 to #6 or any other challenge as long as it is in the scope mentioned in the beginning of this section, namely being TRL 7+, and addressing at least one of the two areas specified in point 2.

2.8 Mapping between challenges and pilot sites on Open Call #1

The following table identifies the challenges each pilot site is intending to address in the Open Call #1 as well as the total number of projects that can be supported.

Table 1 Mapping between challenges and pilot sites

Challenge / Pilot site	Istituto Clinico Humanitas	Hospital Clinico San Carlos	Karolinska Institute
#1 - Early Detection			Yes
#2 - Innovative Diagnostics	Yes	Yes	Yes
#3 - Personalized Care	Yes	Yes	
#4 - Remote Care			Yes
#5 - Healthcare Continuity			
#6 – Recovery			
Total number of startups	2	3	2

3 General provisions

3.1 Funding Scheme

COVID-X funding is **results-driven**, provided as vouchers in a lump sum way. As such, there is no need for a traditional administrative-justification system (e.g. counting hourly dedication or calculating workload), but getting the funding is associated with the full achievement of the relevant milestone.

The selected SMEs or Consortia will be funded as follows²:

Table 2 Funding schema

Funding (% of budget)	When (in Months)	Condition / Event
10%	2	After approval of the KPIs
30%	4	After evaluation of Sprint 1
30%	7	After evaluation of Sprint 2
30%	10	After evaluation of Sprint 3

²

Maximum funding:

- The maximum funding that can be allocated to an SME is 100.000,00 EUR
- The maximum funding that can be allocated to a clinical partner is 50.000,00 EUR

In order to prevent the risk of Double Funding as defined by commission regulations, COVID-X reserves the right to request additional information and pursue due diligence procedures to resolve any doubts.

3.2 Timeline – Acceleration Process #1

Submission to the Open Call of the Acceleration Process #1 (i.e. Open Call #1) will be enabled on the beginning of December 2020 and will end on the 27th of January 2021 at 17:00CET time (Brussels time).

The key dates for the different phases are detailed in the figure below. The opening and closing dates of each phase can be subject to change in case of any modifications in the project's schedule.

Figure 2 Acceleration process #1 Timeline

3.3 Selection process

The full details of the selection process can be found in Annex 2. The phases are as follows:

- I. Eligibility check: to assess if the proposals meet the administrative conditions to apply to the programme;
- II. Pre-screening: to perform quality check and assess project alignment with the goals of the COVID-X project.
- III. Remote evaluation: to rank the proposals by external evaluation committee
- IV. Online interview: to provide top applicants the opportunity of detailing how their solutions will provide the impact expected and how they can benefit from the acceleration programme
- V. Consensus meeting and matchmaking: to assign single solutions to internal healthcare providers and select team solutions

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GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 2: GUIDELINES FOR APPLICANTS

Revision: v.1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016065

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1 Introduction

This document provides a full set of information regarding the COVID-X acceleration process #1 and associated Open Call for Proposals (also referred as Open Call #1). All associated Annexes must be additionally considered for the submission of a Proposal.

General information on the project can be found in annex 1.

2 General information

2.1 Acronyms and definitions

This section describes concepts and terms that will be used in the open call documents. Unless otherwise stated the meaning of an acronym or term is the one stated in this section.

2.1.1 Persons, Entities, and committees

Table 1 Definitions of Persons, Entities, and committees

Term / Expression	Definition
COVID-X Consortium or Consortium	Set of legal entities that are cumulatively responsible to implement the COVID-X project as defined in the Grant Agreement for project number 101016065
Applicant	SME or set of legal entities led by an SME that intends to submit or submitted a proposal to the acceleration programme.
Beneficiary	An SME or a consortium of an SME and Healthcare provider, led by an SME that submitted a proposal to the acceleration programme which was accepted to be funded, and have a signed, or are in the process of signing, a sub-grant agreement.
External Evaluator	Expert hired by the consortium to assist in the evaluation of proposals. External evaluators cannot have conflicts of interest and are bounded by a confidentiality agreement.
Internal evaluation committee	Set of at least 3 persons members of the staff of the consortium, preferably from 3 entities representing the healthcare providers, technical partners, and business partners that are assigned the responsibility of performing evaluations in any stage of the acceleration programme.
Mentor	Person from the consortium that works closely with the beneficiary to foster communication with the consortium and assess progress of the project. The mentor may be part of an evaluation committee.

2.1.2 Acceleration programme

Table 2 Definitions of Acceleration programme

Term / Expression	Definition
COVID-X Acceleration programme or Acceleration Programme	The acceleration programme defined by the set of documents and templates provided by the COVID-X consortium as defined in section 4.1.1. The Acceleration programme is preceded by the application and the onboarding phases and contains 3 phases named as sprints 1 to Sprint 3

Term / Expression	Definition
Single solution	A single solution is a solution proposed by a single SME. Single solutions must meet the conditions mentioned in section 2 of Annex 1 and must focus on the 6 challenges proposed by the clinical partners of the consortium. Single solutions cannot address the open challenge.
Team solution	A team solution is a solution proposed by a consortium of an SME and a Healthcare provider. The SME will act as coordinator of the consortium. Team solutions must meet the conditions mentioned in section 2 of annex 1 and can focus on any of the challenges including the open challenge.
Application phase	Period when applicants can submit proposals to the open call. Each open call has a fixed deadline that is automatically enforced.
Evaluation phase	Period when the consortium evaluates and ranks the applications. In the end of the phase all proposals are notified of the results of the evaluation.
Onboarding phase	Period when the selected proposals and the consortium complete the administrative procedures to sign the sub-grant agreement and prepare administrative and ethical documents.
Sprints 1 to Sprint 3	Successive period of 3 months when the work is performed. In the end of the sprint the project is object of a formal evaluation made by an internal evaluation committee to assess if the project met the proposed goals.

2.1.3 Acceleration programme deliverables

The following subsection defines the deliverables already planned as part of the acceleration programme. Beneficiaries may be required to provide additional data to monitor project implementation.

Table 3 Definitions of Acceleration programme deliverables

Term / Expression	Definition
D1 Full ethics application	TBD
D2 KPIs definition	Deliverable where the KPIs proposed in the application stage are refined, agreed with the mentor, and approved by the consortium. The KPIs will be the tool to assess project performance and must be reported to the mentor.
D3, D4 & D5 Technical report and presentation of sprints 1,2 & 3	Evaluation materials to be provided by the beneficiary to the consortium at the end of each sprint. The report and the presentation will be used by the internal evaluation committee to assess project progress.
F1 Financial statement	Request for payment to be submitted after approval of D2 to D5.

2.1.4 Other concepts

Term / Expression	Definition
Scores in evaluation processes	Unless otherwise stated, all evaluation processes will rank each criterion with marks between 1 and 5. Half point scores are not given. Score values will indicate the following assessments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1: Fail. The proposal fails to address the criterion under examination or cannot be judged due to missing or incomplete information. • 2: Very poor. The criterion is addressed in an unsatisfactory manner. • 3: Poor. There are serious inherent weaknesses.

Term / Expression	Definition
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3: Good. While the proposal broadly addresses the criterion, there are significant weaknesses that would need correcting. • 4: Very Good. The proposal addresses the criterion well, although certain improvements are possible. • 5: Excellent. The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion in question. Any shortcomings are minor.
Overall score	<p>When the evaluation is made by a committee the score of each criteria is computed and rounded to the nearest integer before computing the overall score.</p> <p>Overall score is the sum the scores of each criteria multiplied by the respective weight, rounded to the nearest integer value.</p>
Schedule for payments to Beneficiaries	<p>All payments do beneficiaries are dependent on successful evaluation of deliverables and reception by the consortium of the corresponding financial statement.</p> <p>All payments will be made with undue delay preferably no later than 30 calendar days after the reception of the financial statement.</p>

2.2 Means of submission

The F6S platform (www.f6s.com/covid-x) will be the entry point for all proposals' submission to COVID-X Open Calls. Submissions received by any other channel will be automatically discarded.

Documents required in subsequent phases will be submitted via a dedicated channel, which will be indicated by COVID-X consortium during the sub-granted projects execution.

2.3 Language

English is the only official language for COVID-X. Submissions done in any other language will not be eligible and will not be evaluated. English is also the only official language during the whole execution of the COVID-X programme.

2.4 Documentation formats

Any document requested in any of the phases must be submitted electronically in PDF format without restrictions for printing.

2.5 Data protection

In order to process and evaluate applications, COVID-X will need to collect Personal and Industrial Data. F6S Network Limited, as the Project Coordinator will act as Data Controller for data submitted through the F6S platform for these purposes. The F6S platform's system design and operational procedures ensure that data is managed in compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Each applicant will accept the F6S terms to ensure coverage.

Please note that COVID-X requests the minimum information needed to deliver the evaluation procedures or the acceleration programme. Annexes 6: Bank account information, and 7 Sub-grant

Agreement Template, are provided for reference and will only be requested if the applicant is accepted in the acceleration programme.

Please refer to <https://www.f6s.com/terms> to check F6S platform data privacy policy and security measures.

2.6 Origin of the funds

Any selected proposer will sign a dedicated Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement with the COVID-X consortium. **The funds attached to the Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement come directly from the funds of the European Project COVID-X funded itself by the Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME), and remain therefore, property of the EU until the payment of the balance, whose management rights have been transferred to the project partners in COVID-X via European Commission Grant Agreement Number 101016065.**

As it can be seen in the Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement template (Annex 7), this relation between the sub-grantees and the European Commission through COVID-X project carries a set of obligations to the sub-grantees with the European Commission. It is the task of the sub-grantees to accomplish them, and of the COVID-X consortium partners to inform about them.

3 Proposal Eligibility Criteria

COVID-X invites market-oriented SMEs to provide innovative products to help fight the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.1 Definition of SME

An SME will be considered as such if complying with the European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC¹ and the SME user guide². As a summary, the criteria which define an SME are:

- a. Independent (not linked or owned by another enterprise), in accordance to Recommendation 2003/361/EC.
- b. Headcount in Annual Work Unit (AWU) less than 250.
- c. Annual turnover less or equal to €50 million OR annual balance sheet total less or equal to €43 million.

3.2 SME Eligibility Criteria

An SME is considered eligible for COVID-X Acceleration Process if it complies with ALL the following rules:

- i. It is a legal entity established and based in one of the EU Member States or an H2020 Associated

¹ European Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2003:124:0036:0041:en:PDF>

² SME definition: Please check "User guide to the SME definition" available at <https://op.europa.eu/s/n3t1>

country as defined in H2020 rules for participation³:

- ii. It is a technology provider or technology adopter/user providing innovation to the healthcare.
- iii. Start-ups that do not have yet annual turnover or balance sheets are also considered eligible given that they fulfil the criteria (a) and (b) of section §3.1 at submission time.
- iv. In case an SME is awarded a sub-project, it will remain eligible even if, at a certain point during the sub-project execution, it does not fulfil criteria (b) or (c) of section §3.1.

For British applicants: Please be aware that eligibility criteria must be complied with for the entire duration of the grant. If the United Kingdom withdraws from the EU during the grant period without concluding an agreement with the EU ensuring in particular that British applicants continue to be eligible, you will cease to receive EU funding (while continuing, where possible, to participate) or be required to leave the project. In that case, the rules of H2020 grants will apply.

Please note that a signed version of **Annex 4: Honour Declaration** and **Annex 5: SME Declaration** are mandatory for a proposal submission.

3.3 Proposal Eligibility Criteria

The following proposals eligibility criteria also apply:

- i. Proposals must have a **clear European dimension**, and contribute towards European Union digitization, **targeting clear economic and societal impact**.
- ii. **Each SME may submit only one (1) proposal at COVID-X Open Call #1. Multiple submissions is a disqualify factor.** In case an SME submit more than one proposal, all proposals that they have submitted will be automatically excluded from the evaluation process.
- iii. **SMEs may participate in maximum one (1) accepted sub-project.** SMEs that have entered or have been invited to enter the COVID-X programme, even if they have not signed the contract for any reason, they are automatically excluded from participating in Open Call #2 even if they submit a different proposal.
- iv. **SMEs may re-submit at Open Call #2 a proposal that has not entered Open Call #1.** However, it is mandatory to flag that this is a resubmission and clearly explain the improvements that they have made.
- v. **Proposals from Linked SMEs⁴ must demonstrate that there is no risk of double funding.** The fundamental principle underpinning the rules for public expenditure in the EU states that no costs for the same activity can be funded twice from the EU budget, as defined in the Article 111 of Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1605/2002 of 25 June 2002 on the Financial Regulation. In the case of proposals submitted by linked SMEs, all must clearly state the differences between them including but not limited to, technical aspects, market strategy and team composition, so that it remains no doubt that there is no risk of double funding. In order to properly assess these

³ Association to Horizon 2020 is governed by Article 7 of the Horizon 2020 Regulation. The list of associated countries is available at:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/3cpart/h2020-hi-list-ac_en.pdf

⁴ Please check the definition of Linked SME at “User guide to the SME definition” available at <https://op.europa.eu/s/n3t1> and include the relevant information in annex 5

concerns COVID-X may assign all proposals to the same set of evaluators and, should any doubt remain, exclude all proposals.

- vi. **The maximum amount of direct funding that a SME may receive via COVID-X is 100.000 EUROS via any mean.**
- vii. **The maximum amount of direct funding that a Healthcare provider may receive via COVID-X is 50.000 EUROS via any mean.**

4 Selection to the Acceleration Programme

The indicative number of projects to be selected in the Programme 1 is 7 (Seven) single solutions and 8 (Eight) team solutions.

The indicative number of projects to be selected in Programme 2 is 6 (Six) single solutions and 10 (Ten) team solutions.

Depending on the quality of the proposals and the budget allocation, the consortium may decide to select a different number of projects in the first acceleration programme.

4.1 Open Call #1 Submission

The Open Call submission will follow the steps that are listed in this section:

4.1.1 Open Call #1 publication

The Open call is defined by the following documents:

- **Annex 1: Open Call text**, which provides a full set of information regarding the Open Call for Proposals for the COVID-X project.
- **Annex 2: Guidelines for Applicants**, this document.
- **Annex 3: Proposal Template**, an online application form, available at F6S platform (www.f6s.com/covid-x).
- **Annex 3.1: Proposal Supplement**, a word document providing information on proposal schedule, timing, Ethical & Security details.
- **Annex 4: Honour Declaration**, which declares that all conditions of the acceleration process are accepted by an SME legal representative.
- **Annex 5: SME Declaration**, which evaluates the status of the SMEs participating at an acceleration process.
- **Annex 6: Bank account information**, which collects information on the applicant(s)' bank account where the COVID-X payments will be sent to.
- **Annex 7: Sub-grant Agreement Template**, which provides a template of the sub-grant agreement that the successful applicants will be requested to sign.
- **Frequently Asked Questions & answers** published at the community feed (www.f6s.com/covid-x).

4.1.2 Applicants Registration

Interested applicants should register at the COVID-X F6S page (www.f6s.com/covid-x). This will be the central interface for managing the proposal applications for the remainder of the open calls.

4.1.3 Proposal Preparation

Please follow the steps:

1. For the proposal preparation, the applicants are requested to apply online and answer to all mandatory questions (with no exception) at: www.f6s.com/covid-x
2. Applicants that do not accept the terms and conditions and do not sign and upload to the f6s platform the completed **Annex 4: Honour Declaration** and **Annex 5: SME Declaration** will not be eligible.
3. Be concrete and concise. Questions have characters' limitations. Please examine all the acceleration process/ open call documents and attend the various online and physical events promoted by the COVID-X projects (covid-x.eu/).
4. It is highly recommended to submit your proposal well before the deadline. If the applicant discovers an error in the proposal, and provided the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request the F6S COVID-X team to re-submit the proposal (for this purpose please contact us at support@f6s.com). **However, COVID-X is not committed that resubmission in time will be feasible in case the request for resubmission is not received by the F6S COVID-X team at least 48 hours before the call deadline.**

It is strongly recommended not to wait until the last minute to submit the proposal. Failure of the proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including network communications delays or working from multiple browsers or multiple browser windows, is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance. The time of receipt of the application as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.

4.1.4 Proposals reception

Submissions will be done ONLY via the F6S platform on www.f6s.com/covid-x. A full list of proposers will be drafted containing their basic information for statistical purposes and clarity (which will be also shared with the EC for transparency).

The application reception will close as indicated in Annex1. There will not be any deadline extensions unless there is a Force Majeure situation (e.g. a major problem caused by the F6S platform and not by the proposers, makes the system unavailable for a long period).

4.2 Procedures to enter the Acceleration Programme

4.2.1 Step 1.1: Eligibility

A manual filtering process will be held to discard non-eligible proposals will follow the checklist. Eligibility criteria check will verify:

- a. The proposing entity is a legal entity eligible for EC funding under the rules of H2020 [Y/N]

- b. The proposing entity is an SME as defined in section 3.1 “Definition of SME” [Y/N]
- c. The proposing entity is either a technology provider or technology adopter/user or provides innovation in the target areas of the project [Y/N]
- d. Are the participation rules as expressed in section 3.2 “SME Eligibility” followed [Y/N]
- e. In the case of Team Solutions is the consortium lead by an SME and the second element an Healthcare Provider [Y/N]
- f. Is the participation rule as expressed in section 3.3 “Proposal Eligibility” followed [Y/N]
- g. Is the proposal written in the English Language [Y/N]?
- h. Are all required documentation: **Annex 4: Honour Declaration and Annex 5: SME Declaration submitted correctly** [Y/N]

Proposals being marked as non-eligible will get a rejection letter including the reasons (a to h) for being catalogued as non-eligible. No further feedback on the process will be given.

4.2.2 Step 1.2 Proposals pre-screening

The goal of the pre-screening phase is to filter the proposals that are aligned with the COVID-X project, meet the impact expected and are feasible in the time scope of the project.

The proposals that pass the eligibility check will move to a pre-screening stage where an internal evaluation committee will evaluate the proposals according to the following criteria:

Table 4 Pre-Screening evaluation criteria

Criteria	Description	Weight
Alignment	The proposal is aligned with the challenges or the open challenge as defined in Annex 1. The solution is data driven. The TRL and CE marking is in the scope of the programme	1/3
Impact		1/3
Feasibility	The datasets required are available in the COVID-X Sandbox, the technical integration is feasible in the timeframe of the acceleration programme	1/3

Section 2.1.4 defines how Individual criteria will be scored and how the final score is computed.

In the pre-screening stage the minimum threshold for each criterion is 3 and the minimum overall threshold is 11.

Proposals that do not meet the minimum thresholds will be excluded from the acceleration programme.

4.2.3 Step 1.3: External remote evaluation

An external evaluation board with experience in the health domain, technologies and business development will review each proposal, scoring them based on the following criteria:

Table 5 External Remote Evaluation Criteria

Criteria	Description	Weight
Excellence	<p>Projects must demonstrate a clear set of objectives aligned with the definition of the COVID-X OC and with the general objectives of the project. The Excellence is evaluated according to the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity and pertinence of the objectives; • Excellence, innovation and quality of the objectives. 	1/3
Impact	<p>Applicants must define a clear set of deliverables aligned with the objectives of the OC. Proposals must demonstrate impact on the COVID-X ecosystem and its contribution to meeting the overall project objectives. The impact is evaluated according to the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening the competitiveness and growth of companies by developing innovations meeting the needs of European and global markets; and, where relevant, by delivering such innovations to the markets; • Effectiveness of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the project results (including management of IPR), to communicate the project, and to manage research data where relevant. 	1/3
Implementation	<p>Applicants must provide credible evidence that the project delivery team has the necessary skills, infrastructure and management experience to be able to deliver the project in the timescales and budget specified. The quality and the efficiency of the implementation will be evaluated according to the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan, including appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources, justification of resources; • Describe the solution specification and testing, piloting/ deployment steps that they aim to implement and consequently its value/benefit for the industry; • Detail the overall project cost, the amount of funding requested and how it will be spent. This budget must represent good value for money in the opinion of the evaluation panel selected to evaluate the OC applications • Appropriateness of the skills and experience of the project delivery team. 	1/3

Section 2.1.4 defines how Individual criteria will be scored and how the final score is computed. The threshold for each criterion will be **four (4)**, while the overall score threshold will be **thirteen (13)**. That means if a proposal receives less than 4 in one criterion or less than 13 overall score it is automatically rejected.

Each evaluator will record his/her individual opinion of each proposal on an Individual Evaluation Report. They will then communicate to prepare a single consensus Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) for each proposal, representing opinions and scores on which the evaluators agree and which they will sign.

4.2.4 Step 1.3: Intermediate Ranking and Selection

At the end of the evaluation process all proposals will be ranked in a single list, independent of the topic(s) that it targets. The criteria for the ranking of the proposals will be semi-automatic following the rules below:

- **Rule 1:** The proposals will be ranked based on their overall score (sum of the criterion 1 to 3).
- **Rule 2:** In case following Rule 1 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to proposals that have higher impact (Criterion 2).

In case following Rule 2 there are still proposals in the same position, and the position of on the rank allows places at least one on them in the short list for interview, the COVID-X will invite all the proposals in the same position to the interview process.

4.2.5 Step 1.4 Online interview

The top projects identified in Step 1.3 will be invited to an online interview which aims to deeply understand project concept, team skills & competence, capacity and willingness to exploit the results.

The interview may take 30 minutes. If the evaluation committee needs, the interview may be extended. Applicants will make a pitch presentation of the project of up to 10 minutes and answer questions from the panel during the remaining time.

The interviews will be carried out by 3 internal evaluation board members and will evaluate the following criteria:

Table 6 Online Interview Evaluation Criteria

Criteria	Description	Weight
Concept & Technology	Confirmation of proposed targets and technology fit;	1/4
Business	the viability of the proposed business model; readiness to present to investors & corporates	1/4
Implementation	reliability to reach milestones	1/4
Team	Quality of the team and benefit that the team can extract from the acceleration programme	1/4

Section 2.1.4 defines how Individual criteria will be scored and how the final score is computed.

If during interview applicants do not commit to what has been presented in application form, these will be declassified.

If after the interview the evaluation panel still has doubts the team may be requested to answer additional questions in writing.

4.2.6 Step 1.5 Consensus meeting matchmaking

After the interview's, evaluators will gather to discuss the evaluated proposal, to generate a common scoring, to report the evaluation as well as allocate single solutions to the COVID-X healthcare providers.

The allocation of single solutions to healthcare providers will be made using the following process:

1. Proposals will be ranked according to the overall score of the online interview.
2. Starting from the top, single solutions will be matched with the healthcare providers in the order provided in the application form, Annex 3.1.
3. If single solution proposal cannot be assigned to a healthcare provider because the capacity of healthcare providers is allocated the proposal is rejected.
4. The process follows until all available slots in healthcare providers are occupied or there are no more single solutions eligible to be allocated.

Once the Single Solutions are selected, the budget available for the team solutions is reassessed eventually increasing the indicative number of team solutions to be funded in the first acceleration programme.

The consortium will select the top team solutions from the list until the budget available is allocated.

Notes:

When the consortium needs to untie scores of proposals to decide which will be funded the following rules will apply:

1. The proposal with highest score in the team criteria of step 1.4 will be selected
2. The proposal with highest score in the team business criteria of step 1.4 will be selected
3. The proposal with highest score in the overall evaluation of step 1.3 will be selected
4. The proposal with highest score in the team impact criteria of step 1.3 will be selected
5. The proposal with highest score in the team impact implementation of step 1.3 will be selected
6. The internal committee will convene and decide between the tied proposals to select which one will be selected.

4.2.7 Redress process

Within 3 working days of the delivery of a rejection letter considering the proposal as non-eligible or an ESR that ranks the proposal below the selection borderline, the proposer may submit a request for redress if s/he believes the results of the eligibility checks have not been correctly applied, or if s/he feels that there has been a shortcoming in the way his/her proposal has been evaluated that may affect the final decision on whether to enter the Acceleration programme or not.

In that case, an internal review committee of the COVID-X consortium will examine the request for redress. The committee's role is to ensure a coherent interpretation of such requests, and equal treatment of applicants.

Requests must be:

- Related to the evaluation process or eligibility checks.
- Clearly describe the complaint.

- Received within the time limit (3 working days) from the reception of a rejection letter considering the proposal as non-eligible or the ESR information letter delivered.
- Sent by the SME legal representative that has also submitted the proposal.

The committee will review the complaint and will recommend an appropriate course of action. If there is clear evidence of a shortcoming that could affect the eventual funding decision, it is possible that all or part of the proposal will be re-evaluated.

Please note:

- This procedure is concerned only with the evaluation and/or eligibility checking process. The committee will not call into question the scientific or technical judgement of appropriately qualified experts.
- A re-evaluation will only be carried out if there is evidence of a shortcoming that affects the final decision on whether to fund it or not. This means, for example, that a problem relating to one evaluation criterion will not lead to a re-evaluation if a proposal has failed anyway on other criteria.
- The evaluation score following any re-evaluation will be regarded as definitive. It may be lower than the original score.

Only one request for redress per proposal will be considered by the committee. All requests for redress will be treated in confidence and must be sent to Project Coordinator via the F6S platform.

In case a proposal under the redress procedure is re-evaluated and the new evaluation score is higher, it will be compared with the proposal that has entered the acceleration programme with the lowest ranking. The comparison will use the ranking rules as expressed in Step 1.4. In case the proposal under the redress procedure ranks higher then both proposals will be invited to enter the acceleration phase.

4.3 Onboarding Phase

After the proposal has been accepted the Beneficiary will start the onboarding process. The goal of this phase is to prepare the work to be performed during the acceleration programme. Three processes need to be carried out in parallel:

- Contract Preparation and signature
- Acceleration services tailoring
- Submission of the full ethics application to the relevant Ethical Committee including the study protocol

4.3.1 Step 1.4: Contract Preparation and signature

After the Open Call evaluation conclusion and projects selection, the COVID-X coordinator will start the contract preparation in collaboration with the proposals' coordinator that have been evaluated in the short list. The Contract preparation will go via an administrative and financial checking (and potentially into technical or ethical/security negotiations) based on the evaluators' comments. On a case by case approach, a phone call or teleconference may be needed for clarification.

The objective of the contract preparation is fulfilling the legal requirements between COVID-X consortium and every beneficiary of the call. The items covered will be:

- Inclusion of the comments (if any) in the Evaluation Summary Report of the proposals and mapping to the Sub-grant agreement (contract).
- To validate the status information of the SME, the following documents will be required:
 - **SMEs declaration:** signed and stamped. In the event the applicant declares being non-autonomous, the balance sheet and profit and loss account (with annexes) for the last period for upstream and downstream organizations should also be provided.
 - **Status Information Form.** In case this is not a start-up, it includes the headcount (AWU), balance, profit & loss accounts of the latest closed financial year and the relation, upstream and downstream, of any linked or partner company. In case it is a start-up, legal document of the official founding date.
 - **Legal existence.** Company Register, Official Gazette or other official document per country showing the name of the organisation, the legal address and registration number and a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).
 - In cases where the **number of employees and/or the ownership is not clearly identified:** any other supporting documents which demonstrate headcount and ownership such as payroll details, annual reports, national regional association records, etc. In case it is a start-up, legal document of the official founding date and declaration of ownership.
- **SME Bank account information:** The account where the funds will be transferred will be indicated via a form signed by the SME legal representative and the bank representative. The account should be a business bank account of the SME.

It should be emphasised that each **SME should provide at contract preparation time a valid VAT⁵ and PIC⁶. Failure to provide the VAT number and PIC Number will automatically result in proposal rejection.**

The request, by COVID-X consortium, of the above documentation will be done including deadlines. In general, the sub-project negotiation should be concluded within 2 weeks. An additional week may be provided by the COVID-X coordinator in case of a significant reasoning. In case negotiations have not been concluded within the above period, the proposal is automatically rejected and the next proposal in the reserve list is invited.

At the end of the negotiation phase, the **sub-grantee funding agreement** will be signed between the COVID-X Consortium represented by its coordinator (F6S) and the Budget Holder (UPM) and the beneficiary SME.

Please note:

- I. The sub-grantee funding agreement/contract will cover the complete programme.
- II. **For British applicants:** Please be aware that eligibility criteria must be complied with for the entire duration of the grant. If the United Kingdom withdraws from the EU during the grant period without concluding an agreement with the EU ensuring in particular that British

⁵ To be checked at European Commission services such as http://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/vies/

⁶ To be checked at the European Commission services at <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register>

applicants continue to be eligible, you will cease to receive EU funding (while continuing, where possible, to participate) or be required to leave the project. In that case, the rules of H2020 grants will apply.

4.3.2 Step 2.1: Acceleration services tailoring

During this phase, the Beneficiary and the consortium will identify from the pool of services the ones that will be more relevant to achieve the project goals and design a personalized acceleration programme.

4.3.3 Step 2.3: Submission of the research protocol to the Ethical Committee

The beneficiary must prepare and submit the research protocol for approval by the relevant Ethical Committee before the end of the onboarding phase.

4.4 Sprint 1

Sprint 1 starts in April 1st, 2021 and has the duration of 3 months. The completion of the onboarding phase is desirable as delays will impact but not prevent the success of the project, and the possibility of releasing funds to the beneficiary in the expected timeframes.

The generic goals of Sprint 1 are:

- Define the KPIs to be used in project monitoring (KPIs definition milestone)
- Complete the technical integration with the COVID-X Sandbox
- Get approval from the Ethical Committee

The specific goals of Sprint 1, as well as the initial KPIs to be used to monitor the project are defined by the Beneficiary in Annex 3.1 of the proposal

4.4.1 Step 3.1: KPIs definition milestone

The Beneficiary with support from the mentor will create D1 Project KPIs to be submitted until the end of M01 of the acceleration programme.

The basis for the KPIs are the information included in the Annex 3.1 of the proposal.

The mentor will provide guidance but is not responsible for the deliverable.

4.4.2 Step 3.2: KPIs definition Evaluation

At the end of sub-project's month (M01), a remote review will take place to evaluate the definition of the KPIs. One week before the review, the sub-project coordinator should submit deliverable **D1: KPI definition**.

The review will be performed by an Internal evaluation committee via a teleconference platform (e.g. Skype or WebEx).

The sub-project will make a short presentation of the KPIs.

After the review, the sub-project coordinator will receive a review report, including comments and potential recommendations. The report will also state if the D1 is accepted or not.

- On acceptance of the D1 Deliverable, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to submit a financial statement F1 (template will be provided) requesting the intermediate voucher of 10% of the grant.
- On rejection of the D1 Deliverable, or in case of not satisfactory review, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to resubmit the deliverable, payment will not be made.

4.4.3 Step 3.3: Project implementation

Project implementation will start in M01. The project must complete the work defined in the plan provided in annex 3 of the application.

During this sub-phase, the SME must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training.

The duration of this sub-phase will be approximately 3 months, covering project months M1 to M3.

4.4.4 Step 3.4 Sprint 1 Evaluation

At the end of sub-project month M3, a remote review will take place to evaluate the project progress.

One week before the review, the sub-project coordinator should submit the deliverable D2 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 1.

The review will be performed by an Internal evaluation committee via a teleconference platform (e.g. Skype or WebEx).

The sub-project will make a short presentation of the progress.

After the review, the sub-project coordinator will receive a review report, including comments and potential recommendations. The report will also state if the D1 is accepted or not.

- On acceptance of the D2 Deliverable, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to submit a financial statement F1 (template will be provided) requesting the intermediate voucher of 30% of the grant.
- On rejection of the D2 Deliverable, or in case of not satisfactory review, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to resubmit the deliverable, payment will not be made. The sub-project must continue project implementation.

4.5 Sprint 2

Sprint 2 after successful completion of Sprint 1 and has the duration of 3 months.

The generic goals of Sprint 2 are:

- Validation of the Data Model

- Agreement on IP

The specific goals of Sprint 2 are defined by the Beneficiary in Annex 3.1 of the proposal

4.5.1 Step 3.3: Project implementation

The project must complete the work defined in the plan provided in annex 3 of the application as well as address comments from the reviewers.

During this sub-phase, the SME must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training.

Additionally, the Beneficiary may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

The duration of this sub-phase will be approximately 3 months.

4.5.2 Step 3.4 Sprint 2 Evaluation

At the end of sub-project month M3, a review will take place to evaluate the project progress. The review will be preferably face to face in a venue to be announced.

One week before the review, the sub-project coordinator should submit the deliverable D3 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 2.

The review will be performed by an Internal evaluation committee

The sub-project will make a short presentation of the progress.

After the review, the sub-project coordinator will receive a review report, including comments and potential recommendations. The report will also state if the D1 is accepted or not.

- On acceptance of the D3 Deliverable, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to submit a financial statement F1 (template will be provided) requesting the intermediate voucher of 30% of the grant.
- On rejection of the D3 Deliverable, or in case of not satisfactory review, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to resubmit the deliverable, payment will not be made. The sub-project must continue project implementation.

4.6 Sprint 3

Sprint 3 starts after successful completion of Sprint 2 and has the duration of 3 months.

The generic goals of Sprint 2 are:

- Completion of the feasibility study

The specific goals of Sprint 2 are defined by the Beneficiary in Annex 3.1 of the proposal

4.6.1 Step 3.3: Project implementation

The project must complete the work defined in the plan provided in annex 3 of the application as well as address comments from the reviewers.

During this sub-phase, the SME must participate in various teaching webinars and/or bootcamp events to extend their knowledge on the COVID-X domains and commercialization/business training.

Additionally, the Beneficiary may need to attend one physical event in Europe.

The duration of this sub-phase will be approximately 3 months.

4.6.2 Step 3.4 Sprint 3 Evaluation

At the end of sub-project month M9, a review will take place to evaluate the project progress. The review will be preferably face to face in a venue to be announced.

One week before the review, the sub-project coordinator should submit the deliverable D4 Presentation and Technical report of sprint 3.

The review will be performed by an Internal evaluation committee

The sub-project will make a short presentation of the progress.

After the review, the sub-project coordinator will receive a review report, including comments and potential recommendations. The report will also state if the D1 is accepted or not.

- On acceptance of the D3 Deliverable, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to submit a financial statement F1 (template will be provided) requesting the intermediate voucher of 30% of the grant.
- On rejection of the D3 Deliverable, or in case of not satisfactory review, the sub-project coordinator will be requested to resubmit the deliverable, payment will not be made. The sub-project must continue project implementation.

5 Sub-Projects Execution Summary

5.1 Mentors

Each sub-project will be assigned at least one mentor. The mentor will communicate with the sub-project on a regular basis and in order to overview the progress and provide technical or business advice.

The COVID-X programme requires that the meetings are held once every two weeks. Mentors and teams will decide the schedule and agenda for the meetings

5.2 Evaluations summary

Each project will go through 5 evaluations, each one highlighting the end of a phase.

Table 7 Project evaluations

Evaluation 1			
When	Open Call #1	Estimated project month	Before project start
Mean	Proposal submission		
If successful	The proposal signs the contract and enters the programme phase		
Evaluation 2			
When	COVID-X KPIs definition	Estimated project month	End of M1
Mean	Deliverable D2 KPIs definition.		
If successful	The beneficiary receives 10% of the budget as lump sum		
Evaluation 3			
When	Remote Review	Estimated project month	End of M3
Mean	Deliverable D3: Sprint 1 Technical report and presentation		
If successful	The beneficiary receives 30% of the budget as lump sum		
Evaluation 4			
When	Physical or remote review	Estimated project month	End of M6
Mean	Deliverable D4: Sprint 2 Technical report and presentation		
If successful	The beneficiary receives 30% of the budget as lump sum		
Evaluation 5			
When	Physical or remote review	Estimated project month	End of M9
Mean	Deliverable D5: Sprint 3 Technical report and presentation		
If successful	The beneficiary receives 30% of the budget as lump sum		

The sub-project coordinator should deliver at least one (1) week in advance all relevant deliverables, so that the reviewers will be able to be prepared. During the review, the sub-project members should present their work, answer questions, and demonstrate their experiment.

After each successful evaluation and within **5 working days**, the sub-project coordinator should send the relevant Financial Statement to the coordinator. Additional conditions and eligibility criteria have already been described in the previous sections.

6 Responsibilities of beneficiaries

The selected SMEs are indirectly beneficiaries of European Commission funding. As such, they are responsible for the proper use of the funding and ensure that the recipients comply with obligations under H2020 specific requirements as described in Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020) [1] The obligations that are applicable to the recipients include⁷:

⁷ The obligations described here are not binding and may be modified, refined or additional obligations may be inserted during the sub-project negotiation if needed.

6.1 Conflict of Interest

The beneficiary SMEs must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the sub-project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

They must formally notify to the COVID-X coordinator without delay any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The COVID-X coordinator may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline.

If the sub-contract consortium member breaches any of its obligations, the sub-contract may be automatically terminated. Moreover, costs may be rejected.

6.2 Data Protection & Confidentiality

During implementation of the sub-project and for four years after the end of the sub-project, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at sub-contract signing time ('confidential information').

If a beneficiary SME requests, the Commission and the COVID-X consortium may agree to keep such information confidential for an additional period beyond the initial four years. This will be explicitly stated at the sub-contract.

If information has been identified as confidential during the sub-project execution or only orally, it will be considered to be confidential only if this is accepted by the COVID-X coordinator and confirmed in writing within 15 days of the oral disclosure. Unless otherwise agreed between the parties, they may use confidential information only to implement the Agreement.

The sub-project consortium may disclose confidential information to the COVID-X consortium and to the selected reviewers, who will be bounded by a specific Non-Disclosure Agreement.

6.3 Promoting the action and give visibility to the EU funding

The beneficiary SMEs must promote the sub-project, the COVID-X project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EC.

Unless the European Commission or the COVID-X coordinator requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.), any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem;
- (b) display the COVID-X logo and

(c) include the following text:

For communication activities: *“This project has indirectly received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under project COVID-X (grant agreement No 824509)”*.

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: *“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a sub-project that has indirectly received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under project COVID-X (grant agreement No 824509)”*.

When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempted from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem. Further detailed information on the EU emblem can be found on the Europa web page.

Any publicity made by the beneficiary SME in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author’s views and that the EC or COVID-X project is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The EC and the COVID-X consortium shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the beneficiary SME;
- contact address of the beneficiary SME;
- the general purpose of the project;
- the amount of the financial contribution foreseen for the project; after the final payment, and the amount of the financial contribution actually received;
- the geographic location of the activities carried out;
- the list of dissemination activities and/or of patent (applications) relating to foreground;
- the details/references and the abstracts of scientific publications relating to foreground and, if funded within the sub-project, the published version or the final manuscript accepted for publication;
- the publishable reports submitted to COVID-X;
- any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC and COVID-X in the framework of the project.

The beneficiary SME shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC and COVID-X does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly substantiated request by the sub-project coordinator on behalf of any sub-project member, the COVID-X, if such permission is provided by the EC, may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary’s security, academic or commercial interests.

6.4 Financial audits and controls

The European Commission (EC) will monitor that COVID-X beneficiaries and the beneficiary SME comply with the conditions for financial support to third parties such as set out in Annex 1 of the COVID-X grant agreement and may take any action foreseen by the grant agreement in case of non-compliance vis à vis the beneficiary concerned.

Moreover, the EC may at any time during the implementation of the COVID-X project and up to 5 (five) years after the end of the COVID-X project, arrange for financial audits to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF). The audit procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC. Such audits may cover financial, systemic and other aspects (such as accounting and management principles) relating to the proper execution of the grant agreement. They shall be carried out on a confidential basis.

The beneficiary SME shall make available directly to the EC all detailed information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, with a view to verifying that the grant agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions and that costs have been charged in compliance with it. This information and data must be precise, complete and effective.

The beneficiary SME shall keep all sub-project deliverables and the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies – including electronic copies – of all documents relating to the sub-project contract for up to five years from the end of the project. These shall be made available to the EC where requested during any audit under the grant agreement.

In order to carry out these audits, the beneficiary SME shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the sub-project applicant offices, to its computer data, to its accounting data and to all the information needed to carry out those audits, including information on individual salaries of persons involved in the project. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot at the moment of the audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

On the basis of the findings made during the financial audit, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The Commission may decide not to take into account observations conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

On the basis of the conclusions of the audit, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules.

In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the Commission in order to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

6.5 Sub-project Communication

The sub-project coordinator should:

- Provide any notice be in writing to the COVID-X project coordinator;
- Notify immediately any change of persons or contact details to the COVID-X coordinator. The address list shall be accessible to all concerned.

7 COVID-X Events

COVID-X will organise physical events in Europe to the teams involved. The events will be compulsory to attend in person. At least one representative per team will be required on each event, although it is strongly advised that at least two people attend.

Failing to attend any of the mandatory events defined at the beginning of each phase by COVID-X will automatically disqualify the team from COVID-X programme.

The foreseen events are:

Table 8 List of programme events

Event	Scope	Where	When	Duration	Mandatory
Sprint 2 mid-term event	Business mentoring and/or demo session	TBD	M4 or M5	2 days	Yes
Sprint 2 evaluation	Evaluation of Sprint 2	TBD	End of M6	2 days	Yes
Sprint 3 mid-term event	Business mentoring and/or demo session	TBD	M7 or M8	2 days	Yes
Sprint 3 evaluation & demo day	Evaluation of Sprint 3 and demo day	TBD	End of M9	3 days	Yes

Please note that the locations and dates at the above table are indicative and not binding. They may be modified during the execution of the program.

8 Checklist

- 1) **Does your planned work fit with the call for proposals?** Check that your proposed work does indeed address one of the topics open in this call.

- 2) **Does your proposal address data solutions and artificial intelligence technology?** Check that your proposed work does indeed address the domains of the call in one of the challenges.
- 3) **Is your proposal eligible?** The eligibility criteria are given in chapter 3 “Proposal Eligibility Criteria”. In particular, make sure that you satisfy the minimum participation requirements (entity from eligible countries).
- 4) **Is your proposal complete?** Have you completed all mandatory questions?
- 5) **Does your proposal fulfil questions requests/ comments?** Proposals should be precise, concise and must answer to requested questions, which are designed to correspond to the applied evaluation. Omitting requested information will almost certainly lead to lower scores and possible rejection.
- 6) **Have you maximised your chances?** There will be strong competition. Therefore, edit your proposal tightly, strengthen or eliminate weak points.
- 7) **Have you submitted your proposal before the deadline?** It is strongly recommended not to wait until the last minute to submit the proposal. Failure of the proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including network communications delays, is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance. The time of receipt of the message as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.
- 8) **Have you provided the necessary annexes?**
- 9) **Do you need further advice and support?** You are strongly advised to communicate with the COVID-X team via the COVID-X blog in the F6S platform and via info@covid-x.eu .

Do not forget that it is mandatory the applicant SME to have a valid VAT number and PIC number during contract preparation time.

9 Contacts

The COVID-X consortium will provide information to the applicants only via the F6S blog, so that the information (question and answer), will be visible to all participants.

More info at: <https://covid-x.eu/>

Apply via: <https://www.f6s.com/covid-x/about>

F6S support team: support@f6s.com

Online Q&A: <https://www.f6s.com/covid-x/discuss>

For extraordinary communication need, please contact the Help Desk: info@covid-x.eu .

10 References

- [1] Digital Innovation Initiatives based on European Networks of Competence Centres in H2020, available online at <https://smartanythingeverywhere.eu/smart-anything-everywhere/>
- [2] REGULATION (EU) No 1290/2013 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 11 December 2013 laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 - the

Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)" and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1906/2006

- [3] EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology, "Guidance note on financial support to third parties under H2020", Annex K. "Actions involving financial support to third parties", http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2016_2017/annexes/h2020-wp1617-annex-k-fs3p_en.pdf
- [4] H2020 Call Objective ICT-04-2017 TOPIC: Smart Anything Everywhere Initiative, <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/ict-04-2017.html>

COVID-X Open Call #1

Apply until Jan 27, 2021 - 5PM CET

Hugo & Antonio + 3

DISCUSS

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Sample form ▾

[Update your Startup profile](#)
[Put Startup in stealth mode](#)

Questions

COVID-X Project and Open Call information

For complete information on COVID-X project please visit covid-x.eu.

COVID-X has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065

Coordinator Summary

1 **SME Name ***

Official name of the SME

150

2 **Legal Address ***

3 **Country ***

Country of registration

40

4 **VAT Number ***

15

5 **SME PIC Number**

If the organization does not have a PIC number please register in the Funding and Tenders portal.
ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register
This information is optional on the application stage but is mandatory for contract signing.

12

6 **Name of contact person ***

Primary person to be contacted by BlockIS

7 **Email of contact person ***

Email address of the contact person which will be added to BlockIS mailing lists

8 **Phone number of contact person**

In rare but urgent situations, we need reach quickly to your team. Phone call it still the fastest channel.

20

9 **Please upload the "Annex.4: Honour Declaration" properly fill-in and signed (Max file size 30MB.) ***

You may download template from here: zenodo.org/record/4320027/files/covid-x_Annex_4.docx
Please fill, export to PDF and sign the document before uploading.

[CHOOSE A FILE](#)

10 **Please upload the "Annex 5: SME Declaration " properly fill-in and signed. (Max file size 30MB.)**

You may download template from here: zenodo.org/record/4320027/files/covid-x_Annex_5.docx

Healthcare Provider Summary (only team solutions)

11 **Name**

12 **Legal Address**

13 **Country**

14 **VAT Number**

15 **Healthcare Provider PIC number**

If the organization does not have a PIC number please register in the Funding and Tenders portal.
ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/participant-register
This information is optional on the application stage but is mandatory for contract signing.

16 **Please upload the "Annex.4: Honour Declaration" properly fill-in and signed (Max file size 30MB.)**

This document is only needed for Team Solutions.
You may download template from here: zenodo.org/record/4320027/files/covid-x_Annex_4.docx
Please fill, export to PDF and sign the document before uploading.

CHOOSE A FILE

Proposal Summary

17 **Proposal Type ***

- Single Solution
- Team Solution

19 **Proposal Acronym ***

20

20 **Primary challenge the proposal is addressing**

- #1 Early detection
- #2 Innovative Diagnostics
- #3 Personalized Care
- #4 Remote Care
- #5 Health Continuity
- #6 Recovery
- Open challenge (Only Team solutions)

21 **Proposal Summary ***

500

22 **Infography (Max file size 30MB.) ***

Please upload a document in pdf format, with a scheme/ picture that illustrates the application. The file has a maximum size of 1 page - only schemes/ pictures, not text document)

[CHOOSE A FILE](#)

23 **Please upload the "Annex 3.1: Proposal Supplement" (Max file size 30MB.) ***

You may download template from here: zenodo.org/record/4320027/files/covid-x_Annex_3_1.docx
Please fill, export to PDF and upload.

[CHOOSE A FILE](#)

24 **Did your project received funding, or has pending applications for EU projects? ***

Please answer "No" or mention the calls you have been funded of the calls you are waiting for evaluation. It is allowed to receive funding from multiple programmes as long as the rules for double funding are met. For the sake of transparency COVID-X and INNO4COV-19 will check for duplicate applications.

500

Annexes & Logistics

25 **How did you became aware of the COVID-X programme?**

- European Commission communications Other

Please let us know which social media platform and eventually be more specific on the profile

Type your answer

Please let us know the name(s) of the EU project(s) that provided references to COVID-X

Type your answer

100

Please specify the EC communications that lead you to COVID-X

Type your answer

100

Please specify how you reached COVID-X

Type your answer

100

26 Acceptance of the Data Privacy Policies *

- I accept the data privacy policy as detailed in Annex 2

27 Acceptance of the COVID-X open call conditions

- We have reviewed and accept the terms and conditions

Are you done? Click below to finalize

APPLY TO OPEN CALL

[Terms](#) [Privacy](#) [Data Security](#) [Cookie Policy](#) [Cookie Table](#)

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COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 3.1: PROPOSAL SUPPLEMENT

Revision: v.1.0

Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

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5.4.	Key personnel short CVs involved in the project	10
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1. Proposal details

1.1 What is the type of proposal you are submitting?

- Single solution
- Team solution

1.2 Which challenge are you addressing?

- Challenge 1 - Early Detection
- Challenge 2 - Innovative Diagnostics
- Challenge 3 - Personalized Care
- Challenge 4 - Remote Care
- Challenge 5 - Healthcare Continuity
- Challenge 6 – Recovery
- Open challenge

1.3 Which clinical partners would you like to work with?

For Single solutions only

Please the availability of test sites to support the challenge you are addressing in Annex 1 of the open call

First preference:

- Istituto Clinico Humanitas
- Hospital Clinico San Carlos
- Karolinska Institute

Second preference:

- Istituto Clinico Humanitas
- Hospital Clinico San Carlos
- Karolinska Institute
- No preference

Third preference:

- Istituto Clinico Humanitas
- Hospital Clinico San Carlos
- Karolinska Institute
- No preference

Please provide a brief description of your choices:

1.4 Can your solution be used with multiple languages?

Which languages are currently supported?

- English
- Italian
- Spanish
- Swedish
- Other languages (please specify):

Can the solution be translated into other languages in the timeframe of the project?

2. Application and technology

2.1. What problem are you solving? Why did you decide to tackle it?

2.2. How do you intend to solve the problem? Where is the novelty?

2.3. Which technology are you using and why?

2.4. How do you plan to integrate the Covid Sandbox provided by COVID-X?

Full description of the Sandbox will be released on the last week of December

2.5. Application goals

Please describe the general and specific objectives pursued by the project, applying SMART methodology (Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic, Time-related).

2.6. Which is the current TRL of your solution?

2.7. Which is the status of the CE marking for your product?

2.8. What is the Technological Approach of your solution?

3.IMPACT AND BUSINESS VIABILITY

3.1. Value proposition

3.2. Who are your target customers

3.3. How do you plan to commercialize your solution?

3.4. How can the solution be applied across all European Union member states?

3.5. How do you differentiate your solution from your competitors' solutions?

3.6. Do you have experience with raising external funding(type, amount)?

3.7. What are the expected investments still required to commercialize the solution to market?

3.8. Are there any legal and/or ethical issues/obstacles that you perceive to be associated with your solution?

3.9. On which business/ technological questions are you seeking to receive mentoring?

4. SME/TEAM DESCRIPTION

4.1. Company description

4.2. How many people are working full time in the company and how many will be allocated to the project?

4.3. Key personnel short CVs involved in the project

4.4. Why your team best suited to work together towards addressing the problem

5. CLINICAL PARTNER DESCRIPTION

5.1. Company description

5.2. What is the role of the clinical partner in the project?

5.3. How many persons will be allocated to the project?

5.4. Key personnel short CVs involved in the project

5.5. Why your team best suited to work together towards addressing the problem

6. Project Activities Breakdown & Scheduling

Describe the activities that will take place in your project from the technical point of view. Break down your work to work packages and tasks and provide timing of the different activities and components (e.g. Gantt chart or similar);

This section should answer the question “how are we going to implement the project to reach the defined objectives?”

The allowed font type is “Arial” and the minimum font size is 11 points, the paragraph spacing 6pt and the line spacing single. The page size is A4, and all margins (top, bottom, left and right) should be at least 15 mm (not including any footers or headers).

7. Annex: Ethical/Security Checklist

ETHICAL ISSUES TABLE

	YES
Informed Consent	
• Does the proposal involve children?	
• Does the proposal involve patients or persons not able to give consent?	
• Does the proposal involve adult healthy volunteers?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Genetic Material?	
• Does the proposal involve Human biological samples?	
• Does the proposal involve Human data collection?	
Research on Human embryo/foetus	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryos?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?	
• Does the proposal involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?	
Privacy	
• Does the proposal involve processing of genetic information or personal data (e.g. health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)	
• Does the proposal involve tracking the location or observation of people?	
Research on Animals	
• Does the proposal involve research on animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?	
• Are those animals transgenic farm animals?	
• Are those animals cloned farm animals?	
• Are those animals nonhuman primates?	
Research Involving Developing Countries	
• Use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)	
• Benefit to local community (capacity building i.e. access to healthcare, education etc)	
Dual Use	
8. Research having direct military application	
9. Research having the potential for terrorist abuse	
ICT Implants	
• Does the proposal involve clinical trials of ICT implants?	
I CONFIRM THAT NONE OF THE ABOVE ISSUES APPLY TO MY PROPOSAL	YES/NO

9.1. Ethics

If you have entered any ethics issues in the ethical issue table, you must:

- submit an ethics self-assessment, which:
 - describes how the proposal meets the national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out;
 - explains in detail how you intend to address the issues in the ethical issues table, in particular as regards:
 - research objectives (e.g. study of vulnerable populations, dual use, etc.)
 - research methodology (e.g. clinical trials, involvement of children and related consent procedures, protection of any data collected, etc.)
 - the potential impact of the research (e.g. dual use issues, environmental damage, stigmatization of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing, malevolent use, etc.).
- provide the documents that you need under national law (if you already have them), e.g.:
 - an ethics committee opinion;
 - the document notifying activities raising ethical issues or authorizing such activities

⚠ *If these documents are not in English, you must also submit an English summary of them (containing, if available, the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned).*

⚠ *If you plan to request these documents specifically for the project you are proposing, your request must contain*

9.2. Security

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- Activities or results raising security issues: _____(YES/NO)
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: _____(YES/NO)
- Any potential “dual use” of results: _____(YES/NO)

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 4: APPLICANT DECLARATION OF HONOUR

Revision: v.1.0

Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

Applicant Declaration of Honour

Title of the proposal: _____

On behalf of _____ (Company name) established in _____, (Official SME address), SME VAT number _____, represented for the purposes of signing and submitting the proposal and the Declaration of Honour by _____ (Name of legal representative),

By signing this document, I declare that

- 1) I have the power of legally binding the above-mentioned SME on submitting this proposal.
- 2) Neither the above-mentioned SME nor any linked SME nor any individual member of the proposal team has submitted any other proposal under COVID-X Open Call #1. In case the above-mentioned SME or linked SME or individual member of the proposal team has submitted more than one proposal in this Open Call, all associated proposals will be automatically excluded from the evaluation process.
- 3) I and the above SME that I legally represent are fully aware and duly accept all COVID-X rules and conditions as expressed in COVID-X Open Call documents and all Annexes, and will fully respect any evaluation decision and proposal selection under COVID-X programme
- 4) The information included in the Annex 5: SME Declaration document is true and legally binding.
- 5) All provided information in this declaration is true and legally binding.
- 6) I give the consent and permission to the COVID-X coordinator to use the attached information to contact me for any issue associated with the above application.

SME Legal representative Contact Information:

Title, Name	
Position in the company	
Full Address	
Country	
Email Address	
Telephone	
Mobile	
Signature, Date and stamp	

Declaration of Proposal Resubmission

By signing this declaration of honour, I declare that all provided information below is true and legally binding both for me and for the SME that I legally represent:

1. Select of the following:

I declare that neither the mentioned SME nor any linked SME nor any member of the proposal team to my knowledge has submitted any proposal in Open Call #1 of COVID-X

I declare that the submitted proposal is a resubmission of the following proposal

Proposal Acronym:

Proposal Name:

I declare that the submitted proposal is not a resubmission. However, the mentioned SME or a linked SME or a member of the proposal team has submitted in the COVID-X Open Call #1 the following proposal(s)

Name of the SME	Proposal Acronym

2. I declare that neither the mentioned SME nor any linked SME associated with this proposal have entered or have been invited to enter the COVID-X Open Call #1.

Title, Name	
Position in the company	
Signature, Date and stamp	

Declaration of Honour on exclusion criteria and absence of conflict of interest

By signing this declaration of honour, I declare that all provided information below is true and legally binding both for me and for the SME that I legally represent:

1. I declare that the mentioned SME is not in one of the following situations:

a) it is bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered into an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;

b) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;

c) it has been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organizations;

d) it is not in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed, to be proved by the deliverance of official documents issued by the local authorities, according to the local applicable rules;

e) it or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organization or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;

f) is subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.

2. I declare that the natural persons with power of representation, decision-making or control over the above-mentioned SME are not in the situations referred to in a) to f) above;

3. I declare that:

a) Neither myself or any person that I know is subject to a COVID-X conflict of interest;

b) Neither myself or any person that I know participates, controls, submits or is associated in any way with more than one proposals.

c) I have not made false declarations in supplying the information required by participation in the Open Calls of COVID-X Project or does not fail to supply this information;

d) I am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the abovementioned points a) to f).

e) I am aware and fully accept all COVID-X condition and rules as expressed in COVID-X Open Call documents Annex 1, Annex 2, Annex 3, Annex 3.1, Annex 4, Annex 5, Annex 6 and Annex 7.

4. I certify that the SME that I represent:

- is committed to participate in the abovementioned project;
- has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain its activity throughout its participation in the above-mentioned project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
- has or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out its involvement in the above-mentioned project.

Title, Name	
Position in the company	
Signature, Date and stamp	

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 5: SME DECLARATION

Revision: v.1.0

Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

Declaration on information on the SME qualification

Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name :
Address (of registered office):
Registration / VAT number :
Names and titles of the principal director(s):

Type of enterprise (see explanatory note)

Tick to indicate which case(s) applies to the applicant enterprise:

- Autonomous enterprise
In this case the data filled in the box below result from the accounts of the applicant enterprise only. Fill in the declaration only, without annex.
- Partner enterprise
Fill in and attach the annex (and any additional sheets), then complete the declaration by copying the results of the calculations into the box below.
- Linked enterprise

Data used to determine the category of enterprise

Calculated according to Article 6 of the Annex to the Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the SME definition.

Reference period (*)		
Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)

(*) All data must be relating to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly-established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made in the course of the financial year
(**) EUR 1 000.

Important:

Compared to the previous accounting period there is a change regarding the data, which could result in a change of category of the applicant enterprise (micro, small, medium-sized or big enterprise).

- No
- Yes (in this case fill in and attach a declaration regarding the previous accounting period).

Signature

Name and position of the signatory, being authorised to represent the enterprise:
.....
.....

I declare on my honour the accuracy of this declaration and of any annexes thereto.

Done at
Signature

EXPLANATORY NOTE ON THE TYPES OF ENTERPRISES TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT FOR CALCULATING THE HEADCOUNT AND THE FINANCIAL AMOUNTS

I. TYPES OF ENTERPRISES

The definition of an SME¹ distinguishes three types of enterprise, according to their relationship with other enterprises in terms of holdings of capital or voting rights or the right to exercise a dominant influence².

Type 1: Autonomous Enterprise

This is by far the most common type of enterprise.

It applies to all enterprises which are not one of the two other types of enterprise (partner or linked).

An applicant enterprise is autonomous if it:

- does not have a holding of 25%³ or more in any other enterprise,
- and is not 25%³ or more owned by any enterprise or public body or jointly by several linked enterprises or public bodies, apart from some exceptions⁴,
- and does not draw up consolidated accounts and is not included in the accounts of an enterprise which draws up consolidated accounts and is thus not a linked enterprise⁵.

Type 2: Partner Enterprise

¹ Henceforth in the text, the term "Definition" refers to the Annex to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the definition of SMEs.

² Definition, Article 3

³ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher is applied. To this percentage should be added the holding in that same enterprise of each enterprise, which is linked to the holding company (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2)

⁴ An enterprise may continue being considered as autonomous when this 25% threshold is reached or exceeded, if that percentage is held by the following categories of investors (provided that those are not linked with the applicant enterprise):

- a) public investment corporations, venture capital companies, individuals or groups of individuals with a regular venture capital investment activity who invest equity capital in unquoted businesses ("business angels"), provided the total investment of those business angels in the same enterprise is less than EUR 1 250 000,
- b) universities or non-profit research centres,
- c) institutional investors, including regional development funds,
- d) autonomous local authorities with an annual budget of less than EUR 10 million and less than 5000 inhabitants.

(Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2, second sub-paragraph)

⁵ - If the registered office of the enterprise is situated in a Member State which has provided for an exception to the requirement to draw up such accounts pursuant to the Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, the enterprise should nevertheless check specifically whether it does not meet one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

- There are also some very rare cases in which an enterprise may be considered linked to another enterprise through a person or a group of natural persons acting jointly (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 3).

- Conversely, there are very few cases of enterprises drawing up consolidated accounts voluntarily, without being required to do so under the Seventh Directive. In that case, the enterprise is not necessarily linked and can consider itself only a partner.

To determine whether the enterprise is linked or not, in each of the three situations it should be checked whether or not the enterprise meets one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition, where applicable through a natural person or group of natural persons acting jointly.

This type represents the situation of enterprises which establish major financial partnerships with other enterprises, without the one exercising effective direct or indirect control over the other. Partners are enterprises which are not autonomous, but which are not linked to one another.

The applicant enterprise is a partner of another enterprise if:

- it has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the other enterprise, or the other enterprise has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the applicant enterprise,
- the enterprises are not linked enterprises within the meaning defined below, which means, among other things, that the voting rights of one in the other do not exceed 50%,
- and the applicant enterprise does not draw up consolidated accounts which include the other enterprise by consolidation, and is not included by consolidation in the accounts of the other enterprise or of an enterprise linked to it⁵.

Type 3: Linked Enterprise

This type corresponds to the economic situation of enterprises which form a group through the direct or indirect control of the majority of the voting rights (including through agreements or, in certain cases, through natural persons as shareholders), or through the ability to exercise a dominant influence on an enterprise. Such cases are thus less frequent than the two preceding types.

In order to avoid difficulties of interpretation for enterprises, the Commission has defined this type of enterprise by taking over – wherever they are suitable for the purposes of the Definition – the conditions set out in Article 1 of Council Directive 83/349/EEC on consolidated accounts⁶, which has been applied for many years.

An enterprise thus generally knows immediately that it is linked, since it is already required under that Directive to draw up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the accounts of an enterprise which is required to draw up such consolidated accounts.

The only two cases, which are however not very frequent, in which an enterprise can be considered linked although it is not already required to draw up consolidated accounts, are described in the first two indents of endnote 5 of this explanatory note. In those cases, the enterprise should check whether it meets one or other of the conditions set out in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

II. THE HEADCOUNT AND THE ANNUAL WORK UNITS⁷

The headcount of an enterprise corresponds to the number of annual work units (AWU).

⁶ Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, based on Article 54(3)(g) of the Treaty and concerning consolidated accounts (OJ L 193, 18/7/1983, p. 1), as last amended by Directive 2001/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 283, 27/10/01, p. 28).

⁷ Definition, Article 5.

Who is included in the headcount?

- The employees of the applicant enterprise,
- persons working for the enterprise being subordinate to it and considered to be employees under national law,
- owner-managers,
- partners engaging in a regular activity in the enterprise and benefiting from financial advantages from the enterprise.

Apprentices or students engaged in vocational training with an apprenticeship or vocational training contract are not taken into account in the headcount.

How is the headcount calculated?

One AWU corresponds to one person who worked full-time in the enterprise in question or on its behalf during the entire reference year. The headcount is expressed in AWUs.

The work of persons, who did not work the entire year, or who worked part-time - regardless of its duration - and seasonal work is counted as fractions of AWU.

The duration of maternity or parental leaves is not counted.

ANNEX TO THE DECLARATION CALCULATION FOR THE PARTNER OR LINKED TYPE OF ENTREPRISE

Annexes to be enclosed if necessary

- Annex A if the applicant enterprise has at least one partner enterprise (and any additional sheets)
- Annex B if the applicant enterprise has at least one linked enterprise (and any additional sheets)

Calculation for the partner or linked type of enterprise⁸ (see explanatory note)

Reference period ⁹ :			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1. Data ⁹ of the applicant enterprise or consolidated accounts (copy data from box B(1) in annex B ¹⁰)			
2. Proportionally aggregated data ⁹ of all partner enterprises (if any) (copy data from box A in annex A)			
3. Added up data ⁹ of all linked enterprises (if any) – if not included by consolidation in line 1 (copy data from box B(2) in annex B)			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

⁸ Definition, Article 6 paragraphs 2 and 3

⁹ All data must be relating to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly-established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made in the course of the financial year (Definition, Article 4).

¹⁰ The data of the enterprise, including the headcount, are determined on the basis of the accounts and other data of the enterprise or, where they exist, the consolidated accounts of the enterprise, or the consolidated accounts in which the enterprise is included through consolidation.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in the box "Data used to determine the category of enterprise" in the declaration.

ANNEX A Partner enterprises

For each enterprise for which a 'partnership sheet' has been completed (one sheet for each partner enterprise of the applicant enterprise and for any partner enterprises of any linked enterprise, of which the data is not yet included in the consolidated accounts of that linked enterprise), the data in the 'partnership box' in question should be entered in the summary table below:

BOX A

Partner enterprise (name / identification)	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

(attach sheets or expand the present table, if necessary)

Reminder:

This data is the result of a proportional calculation done on the 'partnership sheet' for each direct or indirect partner enterprise.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 2 (regarding partner enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

PARTNERSHIP SHEET

1. Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name

.....

Address (of registered office)

.....

Registration/VAT number¹¹

.....

Names and titles of the principal director(s)¹²

.....

2. Raw data regarding that partner enterprise

Reference period			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Raw data			

(*) EUR 1 000.

Reminder: These raw data are derived from the accounts and other data of the partner enterprise, consolidated if they exist. To them are added 100% of the data of enterprises which are linked to this partner enterprise, unless the accounts data of those linked enterprises are already included through consolidation in the accounts of the partner enterprise¹³. If necessary, add “linkage sheets” for the enterprises which are not yet included through consolidation.

3. Proportional calculation

- a) Indicate precisely the holding¹⁴ of the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or of the linked enterprise via which the relation to the partner enterprise is established) in the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates:

.....
.....

Indicate also the holding of the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates in the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or in the linked enterprise):

.....
.....

- b) The higher of these two holding percentages should be applied to the raw data entered in the previous box. The results of this proportional calculation should be given in the following table:

¹¹ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

¹² Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

¹³ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, first sub-paragraph

¹⁴ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher. To this holding should be added the holding of each linked enterprise in the same enterprise (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2 first sub-paragraph).

'Partnership box'

Percentage:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Proportional results			

(*) EUR 1 000.

These data should be entered in Box A in Annex A.

ANNEX B Linked enterprises

DETERMINE THE CASE APPLICABLE TO THE APPLICANT ENTERPRISE:

- Case 1:** The applicant enterprise draws up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the consolidated accounts of another enterprise. (Box B(1))
- Case 2:** The applicant enterprise or one or more of the linked enterprises do not establish consolidated accounts or are not included in the consolidated accounts. (Box B(2)).

Please note: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation¹⁵.

CALCULATION METHODS FOR EACH CASE:

In case 1: The consolidated accounts serve as the basis for the calculation. Fill in Box B(1) below.

Box B(1)			
	Headcount (*)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
Total			

(*) Where in the consolidated accounts no headcount data appears, the calculation of it is done by adding the data from the enterprises to which the enterprise in question is linked.

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 1 of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

Identification of the enterprises included through consolidation

Linked enterprise (name / identification)	Address (of registered office)	Registration / VAT number (*)	Names and titles of the principal director(s) (**)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			

¹⁵ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph

6.			
7.			
Total			

(*) To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

(**) Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

Important: Partner enterprises of such a linked enterprise, which are not yet included through consolidation, are treated like direct partners of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' should therefore be added in Annex A.

In case 2: For each linked enterprise (including links via other linked enterprises), complete a "linkage sheet" and simply add together the accounts of all the linked enterprises by filling in Box B(2) below.

Box B(2)

Enterprise No.:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
1. (*)			
2. (*)			
3. (*)			
Total			

(*) attach one "linkage sheet" per enterprise

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 3 (regarding linked enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

LINKAGE SHEET

(only for linked enterprises not included by consolidation in Box B)

1. Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business name

.....

Address (of registered office)

.....

Registration/VAT number¹⁶

.....

Names and titles of the principal director(s)¹⁷

.....

2. Data on enterprise

Reference period			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

These data should be entered in Box B(2) in Annex B.

Important: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation¹⁸.

Such partner enterprises are treated like direct partner enterprises of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' have therefore to be added in Annex A.

¹⁶ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

¹⁷ Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

¹⁸ If the data of an enterprise are included in the consolidated accounts to a lesser proportion than the one determined under Article 6 paragraph 2, the percentage rate according to that article should be applied (Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph).

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX 6: BANK ACCOUNT FORM

Revision: v.1.0

Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ACCELERATION BENEFICIARY AGREEMENT

Revision: v.1.0

Agreement Number	COVID-X-OC1-2021/___
Proposal Title	
Proposal Acronym	

Contracting parties

F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED (F6S), established in 39 Fitzwilliam Place Dublin 2, D02ND6, DUBLIN, Ireland, VAT number: IE3629141FH, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Nuno VARANDAS, acting as an agent of F6S with powers delegated to sign COVID-X contracts.

Hereinafter referred as the “Contractor”

UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (UPM), established in CALLE RAMIRO DE MAEZTU 7 EDIFICIO RECTORADO, 28040 MADRID, Spain , VAT number: ESQ2818015F, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by [UPM please provide], [Position,UPM please provide], legal representative of UPM.

Hereinafter referred as the “Treasurer”

Of the one part,

[COMPANY_NAME], a Company organized under the laws of [COUNTRY], established in [LEGAL_ADDRESS], with VAT number [VAT_NUMBER], duly represented by [LEGAL_REPRESENTATIVE], [LEGAL_REPRESENTATIVE_POSITION],

Hereinafter referred as the “Beneficiary”

Hereinafter collectively referred as the “Contracting Parties”

HAVE AGREED to the following terms and conditions including those in the following Annexes, which form an integral part of this COVID-X Acceleration Process 1 Beneficiary Agreement (hereinafter referred as the “Contract”):

General Provisions

The European Commission (hereinafter referred as the “EC”) and the Contractor, as a member of the COVID-X consortium, have signed the Grant Agreement no 101016065 for the implementation of the project “COVID eXponential Programme” (Acronym: COVID-X) within the framework of the Programme H2020-SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2-CNECT. The Beneficiary has received the favourable resolution by the external evaluators and therefore is entitled to receive funding and services according to the terms and conditions set out under this Beneficiary Agreement and in accordance with the Annex 2: Guidelines for Applicants.

This Contract aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties.

The Funding received by the Beneficiary is property of the EC. The Contractor and Treasurers are mere holders and managers of the funds.

Article 1 – Entry into force & Termination of the contract

1.1 Entry into force

This Contract shall enter into force on the day of its signature by the last Contracting Party. However, late signature of the contract by any of the contracting parties will not affect the execution schedule of the sub-project. The Contractor shall sign this contract, only after all of the following documents have been received from the Beneficiary:

- The original signed Declaration of Honour (as given in Annex 4 of this Contract);
- *SME Declaration* form (as given in Annex 5 of this Contract);
- Copy of ID-card or Passport of legal representative(s) of the SME;
- Copy of the original Extract of SME registration;
- Proof of VAT registration;
- Bank Information Form (as given in Annex 6 of this Contract).

All documents shall be sent to the Contractor first via email to the following address: administrative@covid-x.eu, while the Annexes 1, 2, 3 and 3.1 of this Contract will also be sent as originals, via regular mail, to the following address:

UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (COVID-X Team)
CALLE RAMIRO DE MAEZTU 7 EDIFICIO RECTORADO
28040 MADRID
Spain

The Beneficiary is solely responsible for the accuracy of all data provided to the Contractor.

1.2 Contract Termination

This Contract terminates in the event of unjustified withdraw by the Beneficiary of the current fulfilment of its Contract obligations. “Unjustified withdraw” covers any situation out of “Force Majeure” qualification which determines the absence of performance of the Beneficiary contractual obligations. In this particular case, it entitles the Contractor the right to claim the Beneficiary the full refund of all payments made to the Beneficiary up to date.

Article 2 – Obligations and Responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary are defined in detail in the Annex 2 - Guidelines for Applicants.

Additionally, the Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the Project. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of

interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Contractor without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

Article 3 – Breach of Contractual obligations

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, the Contractor reserves the right to claim the Beneficiary the full refund of all payments made to the Beneficiary up to date. The breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary shall be determined by the COVID-X Consortium or COVID-X Project Coordinator. Not attending the Event (unless in the case of Force Majeure) or attending the Event in a manner which intentionally disrupts the Event, shall be deemed as breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary. The provision of false or misleading declarations by the Beneficiary or any unsolved situation of conflict of interest also constitute examples of breach of contractual obligations by the Beneficiary.

For British applicants: Please be aware that eligibility criteria must be complied with for the entire duration of the grant. If the United Kingdom withdraws from the EU during the grant period without concluding an agreement with the EU ensuring in particular that British applicants continue to be eligible, you will cease to receive EU funding (while continuing, where possible, to participate) or be required to leave the project.

Article 4 – Financial contribution and financial provisions

4.1 Maximum financial contribution

The maximum financial contribution to be granted by the Contractor to the Beneficiary shall not exceed the amount of:

- One Hundred Thousand Euros for SMEs (100,000€)
- Fifty Thousand Euros for Healthcare providers (50,000€).

4.2. Distribution of the financial contribution

The financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary shall be calculated and distributed in accordance with the provisions of the Annex 2: Guidelines for Applicants.

In any case, the financial grant to be paid will always be subject to:

- A favourable resolution by the external evaluators and COVID-X project responsible for assessing the Project in each of the phases;
- Reception and acceptance of the relevant Financial Statement (F1, F2 and F3) of the beneficiary;
- The Beneficiary Bank Account (Annex 6) matches the Financial Statement Bank Account;
- The availability of funds in TREASURER bank account during the relevant payment period;
- Payments to the Beneficiary will be made by the Treasurer. In particular:
 - The Treasurer reserves the right to withhold the payments in case the Beneficiary does not fulfil with its obligations and tasks as per Annex 2 - Guidelines for Applicants;

- Banking and transaction costs charged by any of the banks related to the handling of any financial resources made available to the Beneficiary by the Treasurer shall be covered by the holder of the bank account which originated the cost. This means that the Treasurer bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank and the Beneficiary bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank.;
- Payments will be released no later than thirty (30) natural days after the notification by the Contractor;
- The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this financial contribution.

4.3. Payments schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant phase of the Project as per the Guidelines for Applicants (Annex 2).

The Beneficiary is entitled to receive exclusively those payments allocated to each specific stage of the Project provided that the conditions under Article 4.2 are met.

Article 5 – Right and obligations related to background

5.1 Agreement on background

The beneficiaries must identify and agree (in writing) on the background for the action ('agreement on background').

'Background' means any data, know-how or information — whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights — that:

- (a) is held by the parties before they acceded to the Agreement, and
- (b) is needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

5.2 Data provided by COVID-X Healthcare Providers

The data made available by the Health Care Providers in technical infrastructure developed by COVID-X is owned by the generating party and, in the context of this agreement is considered background.

5.3 Services, products and data provided by sub grantees

Services and products owned by third parties developed prior entering the acceleration programme are considered background.

The data made available by the third party Health Care Providers in technical infrastructure developed by COVID-X is owned by the generating party and, in the context of this agreement is considered background.

Annex 8 to the Sub-Grant agreement identifies all the background that third parties bring to the project, including but not limited to, a description of the TRL level of the product.

Article 6 — Access rights to background

6.1 Exercise of access rights — Waiving of access rights — No sub-licensing

To exercise access rights, this must first be requested in writing ('request for access'). 'Access rights' means rights to use results or background under the terms and conditions laid down in this Agreement.

Waivers of access rights are not valid unless in writing.

Unless agreed otherwise, access rights do not include the right to sub-license.

6.2 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for implementing their own tasks under the action

The beneficiaries must give each other access — on a royalty-free basis — to background needed to implement their own tasks under the action, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement —:

(a) informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel), or

(b) agreed with the other beneficiaries that access would not be on a royalty-free basis.

6.3 Access rights for other beneficiaries, for exploiting their own results

The beneficiaries must give each other access — under fair and reasonable conditions — to background needed for exploiting their own results, unless the beneficiary that holds the background has — before acceding to the Agreement — informed the other beneficiaries that access to its background is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel).

'Fair and reasonable conditions' means appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for access, for example the actual or potential value of the results or background to which access is requested and/or the scope, duration or other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged.

Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

6.4 Access rights for affiliated entities

Unless otherwise agreed in the agreement, access to background must also be given — under fair and reasonable conditions (see above; Article 6.3) and unless it is subject to legal restrictions or limits, including those imposed by the rights of third parties (including personnel) — to affiliated entities established in an EU Member State or 'associated country', if this is needed to exploit the results generated by the beneficiaries to which they are affiliated.

Unless agreed otherwise (see above; Article 6.1), the affiliated entity concerned must make the request directly to the beneficiary that holds the background. Requests for access may be made — unless agreed otherwise — up to one year after the period set out in Article 3.

Article 7 — Ownership of results

7.1 Ownership by the beneficiary that generates the results

Results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them. 'Results' means any (tangible or intangible) output of the action such as data, knowledge or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that is generated in the action, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

7.2 Joint ownership by several beneficiaries

Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if:

- (a) they have jointly generated them and
- (b) it is not possible to:
 - (i) establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary, or
 - (ii) separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection (see Article 27).

The joint owners must agree (in writing) on the allocation and terms of exercise of their joint ownership ('joint ownership agreement'), to ensure compliance with their obligations under this Agreement.

Unless otherwise agreed in the joint ownership agreement, each joint owner may grant non-exclusive licences to third parties to exploit jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license), if the other

joint owners are given:

- (a) at least 45 days advance notice and
- (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

Once the results have been generated, joint owners may agree (in writing) to apply another regime than joint ownership (such as, for instance, transfer to a single owner (see Article 30) with access rights for the others).

7.3 Rights of third parties (including personnel)

If third parties (including personnel) may claim rights to the results, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it complies with its obligations under the Agreement.

If a third party generates results, the beneficiary concerned must obtain all necessary rights (transfer, licences or other) from the third party, in order to be able to respect its obligations as if those results were generated by the beneficiary itself.

If obtaining the rights is impossible, the beneficiary must refrain from using the third party to generate the result

Article 8 – Liability of the Beneficiary

Neither the Contractor nor the EC can be held liable for any acts or omissions of the Beneficiary in relation to this Contract. At the same time, the Beneficiary is responsible for any act or omission that causes damage to the Contractor, the Data Provider, and/or the EC in relation to this Contract.

The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that their acts within the framework of this Contract do not infringe third parties' rights. There is no joint liability between the Contracting Parties.

Article 9 – Confidentiality

With respect to all information of whatever nature or form as is disclosed between the Contracting Parties in connection with the Project and identified in writing as confidential, the terms of this Article shall apply.

The Contracting Parties agree that such information is communicated on a confidential basis and its disclosure may be prejudicial to the owner of the information.

Article 10 – Force Majeure

“Force Majeure” shall mean, any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Contracting Parties control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Agreement, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable in spite of the exercising all due diligence.

Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as force majeure.

The Contracting Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to force majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.

No Contracting Party shall be considered to be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such breach is caused by Force Majeure. A Contracting Party will notify the other Contracting Party of any Force Majeure as soon as possible. In case the Beneficiary is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within 10 (ten) days after such notification, the Contractor will decide accordingly including the termination of the Contract.

Article 11 – Information and communication

Any publicity made by the Beneficiary in respect of the project, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, must specify that it reflects only the author's views and that the Contractor, COVID-X consortium or EC are not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The Contractor, COVID-X consortium and EC shall be authorized to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- the name of the Beneficiary;
- contact address of the Beneficiary;
- the general purpose of the project;
- the amount of the financial contribution of the EC.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorizations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the Contractor, COVID-X Consortium or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly substantiated request by the Contractor on behalf of the Beneficiary, the EC may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

Article 12 – Data protection

12.1. General Data Protection Regulation

The Contracting Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specified purposes and adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed.

The Beneficiary will use and process the data only for the purposes of this Contract and during the length of the Contract. Any unauthorised use is forbidden. In any event, neither the Contractor nor the Data Provider will be held responsible for any abusive use of data incurred into by the Beneficiary.

The Beneficiary shall not to try to re-identify anonymised data. In the event that re-identification occurs, the Beneficiary commits not to use such data.

The Beneficiary shall delete, at the end of this Contract, the data to which the Beneficiary has been granted access during the incubation process, except where an agreement is entered into with the Data Provider.

12.2 National and local laws

Current national and local laws and regulations that may apply where the Validation Pilot will be carried out. Likewise, they will have to observe the guidelines established for this purpose by the European Data Protection Committee and the Control Authorities in the matter of data protection of the respective countries.

12.3 COVID-X Guideline

Guidelines received from the COVID-X consortium, such as the Project Security Policy or those included in the anonymization guide, among others, will be compulsory for the participants.

12.4. New data produced

The Beneficiary acknowledges that he/she will be the “data controller” of any new dataset of piece of personal information that the Beneficiary may produce in the course of the COVID-X project.

Article 13 – Regulations on biomedical research

The project is subject to the European Union regulations on biomedical research and clinical trials.

The beneficiary must take all relevant measures to assure compliance for the entire duration of the project in particular with :

- Regulation (EU) 536/2014 of the European Parliament and Council of April 16th, 2014 on clinical trials of medicinal products for human use (which repeals the Directive 2001/20/EC)
- Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and Council of April 5th, 2017 on medical devices (amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC)
- National and local laws and regulations that may be applicable where the Pilot Validation will be carried out.

Article 14 – Financial audits and controls

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the Project and up to five years after the end of the COVID-X project (foreseen for 31 December 2021), arrange for financial audits to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF), on the Beneficiary. The audit procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC. Such audits may cover financial, systemic and other aspects (such as accounting and management principles) relating to the proper execution of the Grant Agreement. They shall be carried out on a confidential basis.

The Beneficiary shall make available directly to the EC all detailed information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, with a view to verifying that the Grant Agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions and that costs have been charged in compliance with it. This information and data must be precise, complete and effective.

The Beneficiary shall keep the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies – including electronic copies - of all documents relating to the Contract until 2026. These shall be made available to the EC where requested during any audit under the Grant Agreement. In order to carry out these audits, the Beneficiary shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the Beneficiary's offices, to its computer data, to its accounting data and to all the information needed to carry out those audits, including information on individual salaries of persons involved in the project. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot at the moment of the audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

On the basis of the findings made during the financial audit, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The EC may decide not to take into account observations conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

On the basis of the conclusions of the audit, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules. In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the EC in order to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

Article 15 – Amendments

Amendments or changes to this Contract shall be made in writing and signed by the duly authorized representative of the Contracting Parties. Nevertheless, In the event the EC modifies the conditions, the Contractor will amend the Contract accordingly.

Article 16 – Language

This contract is drawn up in English, language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings and processes relative thereto.

Article 17 – Applicable Law

This Contract shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium.

Article 18 – Settlement of disputes

Annexes

TEMPLATE for FP7 Competitive Calls and H2020 Financial Support to Third Parties

To publish a call on the Funding & Tenders Portal (F&TP), the Project Officer must send to the F&TP team at least the following information:

	Information to be provided by the project consortium
Call title:	COVID-X Open Call #1
Full name of the EU funded project:	COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME
Project acronym:	COVID-X
Grant agreement number:	H2020-101016065
Call publication date:	<i>14 December 2020</i>
Call deadline:	<i>27 January 2021 at 17:00 (Brussels time)</i>
Expected duration of participation:	<i>9 months</i>
Total EU funding available:	Funding available for this acceleration process: 1.900.000€. Indicative number of funded solutions: 7 Single Solution*100.000€ 8 Team Solutions * 150.000€
Submission & evaluation process:	<p>COVID-X will bridge the collaboration divide between eHealth solution providers -with emphasis on lean startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)-, and the healthcare professional system to fight COVID-19. The purpose is to boost an end-to-end agile validation programme of cutting-edge technology in three real-world clinical scenarios, located in hotspots of the pandemic: Italy, Spain and Sweden.</p> <p>The project will fast-track value streams between the two poles under consideration: 1) attract, invest and empower a community of European eHealth SMEs –the beneficiaries of an acceleration program, selected by open calls- that will provide market-ready fast, cost-effective and easily deployable sampling, screening, diagnostic and prognostic systems and/or data-driven services and tools, already certified with -or close to receive- the CE marking (type 1 of the call); 2) actively involve some of the most relevant hospitals of Europe that have the resources, critical mass and ambition to scale-up their capabilities in the COVID-19 response; thanks to the support of an innovative data</p>

	<p>sandbox, released as an in-house asset of COVID-X, to facilitate access easily, uniformly and securely to various health data sources, and providing data services including Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based decision support systems, data security, visual analytics and intuitive dashboards capabilities. The project will invest dedicated efforts to enforce data privacy and security, ethical compliance and user acceptance.</p> <p>Besides a solid consortium to access high-level startups/SMEs, deliver highly valuable technological & business services, provide an innovative data Sandbox with AI capabilities for COVID related services and access 3 piloting sites, COVID-X targets to attract +155 applications and select 31 to undertake through the COVID-X Programme, investing a total of 4M€ in high impact solution providers.</p> <p>Selection process</p> <p>The full details of the selection process can be found in Annex 2. The phases are as follows:</p> <p>I. Eligibility check: to assess if the proposals meet the administrative conditions to apply to the programme;</p> <p>II. Pre-screening: to perform quality check and assess project alignment with the goals of the COVID-X project.</p> <p>III. Remote evaluation: to rank the proposals by external evaluation committee</p> <p>IV. Online interview: to provide top applicants the opportunity of detailing how their solutions will provide the impact expected and how they can benefit from the acceleration programme</p> <p>V. Consensus meeting and matchmaking: to assign single solutions to internal healthcare providers and select team solutions</p> <p>Submissions are available via https://covid-x.eu</p>
Further information:	Details available at https://covid-x.eu
Task description:	The third-party technology providers selected in the COVID-X open calls will enter the CovidProgramme. This programme has been specifically designed to

	<p>provide capacity-building support services to validate and accelerate the market uptake of the selected solutions in the fight against COVID-19.</p> <p>Specifically, during the programme, the COVID-X consortium partners will provide a wide range of free support services based on the identified and concrete needs of the selected applicants. These tailor-made services will be specified during the onboarding phase and company's analysis and can go from business, technical and technology trainings to mentoring and coaching sessions, tech courses, demo-days, info sessions and others.</p> <p>CovidProgramme will follow the already mentioned three sprints approach: 1) Onboarding the technology provider where an initial analysis of the business maturity and needs, matchmaking with appropriate testbed and business mentor takes place; 2) Capacity building where technology mentoring and business development roadmap creation takes place; 3) Acceleration and implementation of roadmap with the involvement of technology and business mentors.</p>
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Additional information may also be required/presented:

Funding scheme/type of action, thematic priority, contract type, project status, project/research costs and funding, eligibility requirements, evaluation criteria, proposal format, project coordinator...